



*Asteromphalus flabellatus*



*Asteromphalus hiltonianus*



*Asteromphalus hookeri*



*Asteromphalus hyalinus*



*Asteromphalus imbricatus*



*Asteromphalus parvulus*



*Asteromphalus pettersonii*



*Asteromphalus robustus*



*Azpeitia africana*



*Azpeitia barronii*



*Azpeitia neocrenulata*



*Azpeitia nodulifera*



*Azpeitia tabularis*



*Bacteriastrum hyalinum*



*Campyloneis grevillei*



*Cestodiscus denarius*



*Chaetoceros affinis*



*Chaetoceros atlanticus*



*Chaetoceros bulbosus*



*Chaetoceros capreolus*



*Chaetoceros cinctus*



*Chaetoceros compressus*



*Chaetoceros constrictus*



*Chaetoceros debilis*







*Fragilaria construens*



*Fragilariopsis curta*



*Fragilariopsis cylindrus*



*Fragilariopsis doliolus*



*Fragilariopsis kerguelensis*



*Fragilariopsis linearis*



*Fragilariopsis obliquecostata*



*Fragilariopsis oceanica*



*Fragilariopsis peragallii*



*Fragilariopsis pseudonana*



*Fragilariopsis ritscheri*



*Fragilariopsis separanda*



*Fragilariopsis sublinearis*



*Gomphonema lanceolatum*



*Gomphonema olivaceum*



*Hemidiscus karstenii*



*Melosira granulata*



*Navicula directa*



*Navicula hennedyi*



*Navicula pygmaea*



*Neodenticula seminae*



*Nitzschia angulata*



*Nitzschia bicapitata*



*Nitzschia braarudii*



*Nitzschia interruptestriata*



*Nitzschia kolaczekii*



*Nitzschia punctata*



*Nitzschia sicula*



*Nitzschia turgiduloides*



*Nitzschia vanheurckii*



*Odontella weissflogii*



*Paralia sulcata*



*Pleurosigma directum*



*Podosira glacialis*



*Porosira glacialis*



*Porosira pseudodenticulata*





*Shionodiscus gracilis*



*Shionodiscus oestrupii*



*Shionodiscus poroseriatus*



*Shionodiscus trifultus*



*Stellarima stellaris*



*Stephanopyxis californica*



*Stephanopyxis dimorpha*



*Stephanopyxis kulmii*



*Thalassionema nitzschioides*



*Thalassiosira antarctica*



*Thalassiosira decipiens*



*Thalassiosira eccentrica*



*Thalassiosira elliptipora*



*Thalassiosira fasciculata*



*Thalassiosira ferelineata*



*Thalassiosira gracilis*



*Thalassiosira gravida*



*Thalassiosira hyalina*



*Thalassiosira kozlovii*



*Thalassiosira kryophila*



*Thalassiosira lentiginosa*



*Thalassiosira lineata*



*Thalassiosira nidulus*



*Thalassiosira nordenskiöldii*



*Thalassiosira oliverana*



*Thalassiosira pacifica*



*Thalassiosira subtilis*



*Thalassiosira symbolophora*



*Thalassiosira symmetrica*



*Thalassiosira tumida*



*Thalassiothrix antarctica*



*Thalassiothrix frauenfeldii*



*Thalassiothrix vanhoeffenii*



*Trachyneis aspera*



*Trichotoxon reinboldii*

